

Quantum Mechanics and a Classical Gas

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Quantum mechanics has been linked to a classical gas in the literature (1). In this note we consider that a classical gas involves impulse hits (momentum transfers) due to statistical two body collisions, either between gas molecules or with molecules in the container wall which is also at temperature T . The key point we argue is that statistical impulse hits occur which seems to lead to a logical inconsistency because all gas particles are stopped by the wall, even a very thin one. This does not seem to be in keeping with the idea of stochastic impulse hits and a Maxwell-Boltzmann energy distribution. In fact, a scenario of stochastic hits should allow for gas particles to leak out of the wall. Due to this inconsistency, one may have a sharp drop off of gas density at the wall.

Quantum mechanics in fact allows for the possibility of particles leaking through a wall by considering impulse hits with no “special hidden mechanism” which blocks particles. There seem, however, to be consequences of considering probabilities and impulse hits. In particular, one is led to complex conditional probabilities $\exp(ipx)$ which are able to interfere (add as well as subtract which classical probability does not do) in order to create a spatial density of zero at the wall. The quantum probability is nonlocal as probabilities $\exp(ipx)$ sense lengths proportional to $1/p$ and are able, through superposition, to “regulate” densities at boundary conditions without the need for a “hidden” mechanism (which is not in keeping with stochastic impulse hits) to block particles beyond a certain point.

In this note we consider the above ideas and examine the infinite well potential which allows for a link between building block probabilities $\exp(ipx)$ and a probability profile with an enforced length (i.e. probability dropping to zero at the potential walls). We also consider the dependence of intrinsic entropy on a change in x range of the infinite potential system.

Classical Mechanics and Statistical Mechanics

Classical mechanics is based on knowledge of a particle $x(t)$ and forces which accelerate the particle at each x . Thus for a classical bound state problem one has turning points which represent places at which the force has decelerated the particle to a velocity of zero before accelerating it again in the opposite direction. This idea seems to have somehow crept into classical statistical mechanics, which, as its name implies, is supposed to deal exclusively with stochastic impulse hits (momentum transfers) at least in an ideal gas.

In particular, classical gas particles may stochastically undergo impulse hits with each other or with molecules in the container wall which is at a temperature of T . If only stochastic hits occur at the container wall, then gas particles should be able to penetrate the wall because there is no mechanism to guarantee they are stopped. Classical statistical mechanics, however, implicitly assumes that gas particles are stopped at the wall otherwise one would not have equilibrium due to leakage. Thus we argue that there seems to be a logical inconsistency in classical statistical mechanics. We further argue that quantum mechanics removes this inconsistency, but that this leads to nonclassical consequences.

Quantum Mechanics

Quantum mechanics we argue is based solely on impulse hits (momentum transfers) together with probabilities. As argued in previous notes, probabilities must be both positive and negative in order to create regions with low or dying probabilities e.g. near a high potential wall. In the case of an infinite potential, the probabilities related to different momenta (impulse hits) must cancel to create an overall probability of zero outside the well. One might argue that probabilities associated with some momenta might be all positive and others all negative, but there seems to be no reason to differentiate between so-called all positive momenta and all-negative momenta. A more reasonable solution seems to be to have oscillating probabilities associated with each momentum. This leads to the introduction of a length scale or resolution for each momentum. Furthermore, oscillating probabilities suggest probability appearing and disappearing which is unphysical and so one might need two dimensions, each with an oscillating probability, and an overall modulus of one to counter this. (These ideas have been suggested in our earlier notes.)

In this note we examine the case of the infinite potential and assume intrinsic probabilities of $F(p,x)$ such that:

$$\text{Conditional probability} = W(x) = \sum_p a(p) F(p,x) \quad ((1))$$

Each $F(p,x)$ is associated with a momentum p and kinetic energy $pp/2m$. We assume that there exists an operator O such that $O F(p,x) = pp/2m F(p,x)$. In other words one has an eigenvalue situation. If that is the case, then for a superposition of $F(p,x)$ as given in ((1)) in a free region (i.e. the region between the infinite potential walls) one has:

$$O F(p,x) = pp/2m F(p,x) \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{and} \quad [O W(x)] / W(x) = \text{kinetic energy} \quad ((2b))$$

In other words ((2a)) and ((2b)) satisfy the same equation even though kinetic energy in ((2b)) is an average value. As a result $F(p,x)$ and $W(x)$ must be of the same form. $W(x)$ is really $W(\text{pave},x)$ and $W(x=0)=0=W(x=L)$ if the infinite potential walls are at $x=0$ and $x=L$. Thus $W(x)$ looks like a symmetric periodic type of object with one piece of the periodic series existing within $[0,L]$. As a result $F(p,x)$ must be of the same form. This is interesting because for $W(x,\text{pave})$ in the well, it is the well which is forcing the probability to drop to zero at 0 and L, but for $F(p,x)$ there is no such restriction, but $F(p,x)$ also carries an intrinsic length linked to its spatial period.

Quantum Mechanics and the Classical Gas

In (1) it is noted that if a quantum particle is in an infinite potential well and if the walls are moved slowly (adiabatically) then $dE = PdL$ where P (pressure) is proportional to pave^2 . This is proved for both the nonrelativistic and relativistic cases. Thus the authors of (1) liken a quantum particle in an infinite well to an ideal gas.

The ideal gas law is $P=n/V RT$ where R is a constant. The first law of thermodynamics yields $dE=TdS-PdV$, but for $dS=0$, $dE=PdV$. $dV=dL$ in one dimension and $P=(1/L) RT$. For an ideal gas

T is proportional to T. Thus $dE = (1/L) dL$ implying that if L is changed, E will change. E and T, however, may take any value.

In quantum mechanics E is a function of L because of the boundary conditions that probability disappears at 0 and L. If one moves the walls slowly, a particle (in say) the ground state stays in this state (adiabatic theorem). One might argue that this means $dS = 0$ and so $dE = PdL$. One knows $E = (1/2m) (2\pi\hbar/L)^2 (n)^2$ ($n =$ level) so this yields an expression for P. Thus the authors of (1) liken the quantum problem to the classical ideal gas. (In general, classical statistical mechanics is believed to have quantum mechanics as its underlying theory as the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein distributions (based on quantum features) become the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution under certain conditions. There are also other features based on quantum mechanics like a $1/(N!)$ factor for identical particles which have quantum mechanical roots.)

In the case of ideal gas analogy, the fact that a quantum state has $E = (1/2m) (2\pi\hbar/L)^2 (n)^2$ guarantees that for an adiabatic expansion $dE = \text{function}(L) dL$, so one may try to associate $\text{function}(L)$ with a kind of pressure.

Intrinsic Entropy

The adiabatic approach assumes that because a particle stays in the same quantum state which changes due to changes in a parameter (here L), that entropy does not change. In the literature (2), however, two expressions are linked to internal entropy of a quantum state i.e.

$$S \text{ density } (x) = W^*(x)W(x) \ln[W^*W] \quad ((3a)) \text{ and } S \text{ density } (p) = a^*(p)a(p) \ln[a^*(p)a(p)] \quad ((3b))$$

In a previous note (3) we suggested that $W(x) a(p) \exp(-ipx)$ (for a bound state) be used as the probability in Shannon's entropy instead of $W^*(x)W(x)$ or $a^*(p)a(p)$ separately. In such a case, we found that entropy density of a quantum state is:

$$\int dx W(x)W(x)\ln(W(x)) + \int dp a(p)a(p) \ln(a(p)) + \int dx dp ipx W a(p) \exp(-ipx) \quad ((4))$$

The last term in ((4)) is equivalent to $\int dx (-i) W(x) x d/dx W(x)$ if $a(p) = a(-p)$ or

$$\int dx \{ (-i) d/dx (WWx) + i WW \} = i 1 \text{ because } WWx \text{ should be zero at the endpoints.}$$

Thus ((4)) is a sum of the spatial and momentum entropies. For the case of a particle in an infinite well one has from (2):

$$W(x) = \sqrt{2/L} \sin(2\pi x/L) \text{ and } a(p) = \sqrt{L} [2\pi/(2\pi + pL) \text{sinc}(.5(2\pi - pL))]$$

If one considers:

$$\int dx WW \ln(WW) = \ln(2/L) 1 + \int dx WW \ln(\sin(2\pi x/L)) \text{ where } x \rightarrow 0 \text{ to } L$$

Letting $y = 2 \cdot 3.14x/L$ shows that $\int W W \ln(WW) = -\ln(L) + \text{constant}$ in terms of L ((5))

For the momentum case $\int dp a(p)a(p) \ln[a(p)a(p)]$ yield a term proportional to $\ln(L)$ and L times an integral of dp from $-\infty$ to ∞ with terms with $n \cdot 3.14 + pL$ and $n \cdot 3.14 - pL$. Let $y = n \cdot 3.14 - pL$. $dp = -dy/L$ so L cancels the L factor in front of the integral. $n \cdot 3.14 + pL = -2 \cdot 3.14n + y$. Thus the momentum entropy yields $\ln(L) + \text{constant}$ in terms of L ((6))

Adding ((5)) and ((6)) yields no dependence on L so $dS=0$ for an adiabatic change of L in an infinite potential where S is the internal entropy consisting of the sum of the spatial and momentum entropies.

Conclusion

In conclusion we argue that a classical statistical gas in a container undergoes stochastic impulse hits (either between gas particles or with particles in the wall), but that a hidden mechanism exists which is nonstatistical and prevents any gas particles from escaping through the wall. Quantum mechanics, on the other hand, we argue is based purely on stochastic impulse hits and their associated probabilities. Thus a quantum particle can in general leak through a potential barrier. By using only impulse hits and their associated probabilities, one must have $F(p,x)$ i.e. a component probability which depends on p and x and allow for these to interfere i.e. add or subtract unlike classical probabilities in order to make probabilities drop quickly or even vanish in the infinite potential case.. Next we consider a quantum particle in an infinite potential well for which overall conditional probability must vanish at $x=0$ and $x=L$. If an operator O exists such that $O F(p,x) = p/2m F(p,x)$ then $O W(x) = E W(x)$ where $W(x)$ is the superposition of $F(p,x)$ values. Thus $W(x)$ satisfies the same equation as $F(p,x)$, but with a special pave. Thus $F(p,x)$ appears to be periodic.

In (1) it is suggested that if one changes L for the square well potential, the work done equals the change dE . This suggests that entropy does not change. From the adiabatic theorem, a particle in a given quantum state remains in that state although it is now characterized by a new L . This suggests $dS=0$. We consider the intrinsic entropy of a quantum state using a Shannon's probability = $W a(p) \exp(-ipx)$ where $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ and find that entropy is the sum of a spatial part and a momentum part. Using values for $W(x)$ and $a(p)$ from (2) we find that S is independent of L so that changing L adiabatically leads again to $dS=0$.

(In another note we had suggested that $a(p1) \exp(ip1x) a(p2) \exp(ip2x)$ might be a candidate for a Shannon's probability, but $W(x) a(p) \exp(-ipx)$ seems to work in the adiabatic case of changing L considered in this note.

References

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